

Photocatalytic bleaching of Trypan blue over zinc oxide – particulate system

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Abstract : Trypan blue (TB) and its mixture with Brilliant cresyl blue (BCB) were degraded photocatalytically in presence of zinc oxide. Efforts made to optimize the conditions for photobleaching of these dyes by various parameters like concentration of TB, pH, amount of semiconductor, light intensity, etc.

Keywords : Trypan blue, zinc oxide, photocatalytic effect.

Various technologies and methodologies are available for removing colour from water which are not cost-effective. In the present paper, we have reported the photocatalytic bleaching of TB which is extensively used in dyeing, printing and textile industries

Materials and methods :

Trypan blue (TB), Brilliant cresyl blue (BCB) and zinc oxide all were analytical reagents. The stock solution ($1.00 \times 10^{-3} M$) of Trypan blue was prepared in doubly distilled water (0.0961 g/100 mL). Some controlled experiments were carried out to confirm that this reaction follows photocatalytic pathway. 0.60 g of zinc oxide was added to 50.0 mL of $2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$ TP solution. The desired pH of the solution was adjusted by addition of previously standardized $H_2SO_4/NaOH$ solutions. The pH of the solution was measured by a digital pH meter (Systronics model 335).

A 500 W tungsten lamp (Mysore) was used for irradiation. The intensity of light was measured by a Surya Mapi (CEL SM 201) solarimeter. A water filter was used to cut-off thermal radiations. The progress of the reaction was measured using a spectrophotometer (Systronics model 116). The solution was made free from ZnO particles and other impurities by centrifuging before absorbance measurements (Remi model 1258).

Results and discussion

The photocatalytic bleaching of TB was observed at $\lambda_{max} = 607$ nm. Absorbance at 607 nm (for TB) decreases with time, becoming negligible finally. The optimum condition was obtained at :

[TB] = $2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$, light intensity = 50.0 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 8.00, ZnO = 0.60 g and temperature = 308 K.

Table 1. Typical run

[TB] = $2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$, [BCB] = $2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$, light intensity = 50.0 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 8.00, ZnO = 0.50 g, Temp. = 308 K

Time (min)	TB ($\lambda_{max} = 607$ nm)		BCB ($\lambda_{max} = 622$ nm)	
	O.D.	2 + log O.D.	O.D.	2 + log O.D.
0.0	0.540	1.7324	0.580	1.7634
30.0	0.484	1.6848	0.541	1.7322
60.0	0.450	1.6532	0.499	1.6981
90.0	0.399	1.6010	0.450	1.6535
120.0	0.349	1.5428	0.423	1.6263
150.0	0.326	1.5132	0.380	1.5798
180.0	0.294	1.4683	0.344	1.5366
210.0	0.276	1.4409	0.306	1.4857
240.0	0.239	1.3784	0.267	1.4265

$k_T = 5.11 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_B = 5.11 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

TB name is : 3,3'-[(3,3'-Dimethyl{1,1'-biphenyl}-4,4'-diyl)bis(azo)]bis[5-amino-4-hydroxy-2,7-naphthalene-disulphonic acid] tetra sodium salt

Table 2. Effect of various parameters

pH ^a	$k \times 10^5$ (s ⁻¹)	[TB] ^b $\times 10^5$ (M)	$k \times 10^5$ (s ⁻¹)	[BCB] ^c $\times 10^5$ (M)	$k \times 10^5$ (s ⁻¹)	ZnO ^d (g)	$k \times 10^5$ (s ⁻¹)	I ^e (mW cm ⁻²)	$k \times 10^5$ (s ⁻¹)
7.00	3.20	1.00	1.28	1.00	2.56	0.20	2.56	50.0	5.11
7.50	3.84	1.50	1.92	1.50	3.20	0.30	3.84	42.0	4.48
8.00	5.11	2.00	3.20	2.00	4.48	0.40	4.48	30.0	3.84
8.50	4.48	2.50	5.11	2.50	5.11	0.50	5.11	24.0	3.84
9.00	3.84	3.00	2.56	3.00	3.84	0.60	5.11	20.0	3.20

^a[TB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, [BCB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, ZnO = 0.50 g, light intensity = 5 mW cm⁻².

^b[BCB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, pH = 8.00, ZnO = 0.50 g, light intensity = 5 mW cm⁻².

^c[TB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, pH = 8.00, ZnO = 0.50 g, light intensity = 5 mW cm⁻².

^d[TB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, [BCB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, pH = 8.00, light intensity = 5 mW cm⁻².

^e[TB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, [BCB] = 2.50×10^{-5} M, pH = 8.00, ZnO = 0.50 g.

The plot of $2 + \log$ absorbance vs exposure time is a straight line which indicates that the photocatalytic bleaching of TB follow pseudo-first order kinetics.

The effect of pH on the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of TB was also investigated. ZnO dissolves in acidic medium, and therefore, photocatalytic bleaching of TB could not be investigated in lower pH range. The rate of photocatalytic bleaching of TB increases with increase in pH up to 8.00 and then decreases. This behavior may be explained on the basis of an increase in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching due to increased availability of OH⁻ ions at higher pH. OH⁻ ions will generate more hydroxyl radicals (*OH), by combining with holes which are considered responsible for the photocatalytic bleaching.

Above pH 8.0, more OH⁻ ions will compete with the anionic dye for adsorption on semiconductor surface. OH⁻ ions will make the surface of the semiconductor negatively charged and as a consequence the approach of TB molecules to the semiconductor surface will be retarded due to repulsive force between two negatively charged species (OH⁻ ions and the electron rich dye). This will result corresponding into a decrease in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of TB dye at higher pH value i.e. pH > 8.0.

The effect of dye concentration on the rate of the reaction was studied by using different concentrations of the TB solution. As the concentration of TB increases, the rate of photocatalytic bleaching also increases, reaching a maximum at 2.50×10^{-5} M. Further increase in concentration of dye resulted into a decrease in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching. It may be due to the fact that as the concentration of the dye was increased, more dye molecules were available for excitation to form singlet and consecutive energy transfer to form triplet dye molecules. But if the concentration of TB

was increased above 2.50×10^{-5} M, the dye will start acting as a filter for the incident light. It will prohibit the desired light intensity to reach the dye molecules near the semiconductor particles and thus; a decrease in the rate of photocatalytic bleaching was observed.

The rate of reaction increases with increase in the amount of ZnO up to 0.60 g. Beyond 0.60 g, the rate of reaction becomes vertically constant. This may be due to that as the amount of semiconductor was increased in the initial stage, the exposed surface area of the semiconductor also increases, but after this limiting value (0.60 g), any further increase in the amount of semiconductor will not increase the exposed surface area but only the thickness of the semiconductor layer. This was also confirmed by using reaction vessels of different dimensions.

The FT-IR spectra of ZnO were recorded in dry and wet state as well as at the end of the experiment. It is clear from the FT-IR spectral data that there is no reasonable change, in the nature of ZnO during this photocatalytic process. Thus, ZnO remains intact or it is regenerated back.

The effect of light intensity on the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of TB show that an increase in light intensity increases the rate of photocatalytic bleaching. As the intensity of light was increased, the number of photons striking per unit area of the semiconductor (ZnO) also increases. An almost linear behavior between light intensity and the rate of reaction was observed. Since an increase in the light intensity increases the temperature of dye solution also when a thermal reaction may occur, therefore, higher intensities were avoided.

Photocatalytic bleaching of mixture (anionic dye TB and cationic dye BCB) was also investigated. The results are reported in Table 1. The effect of various parameters like pH, BCB concentration, TB concentration, amount of

Note

semiconductor, intensity etc. were also studied and reported in Table 2.

It was observed that in the mixture of dye (BCB + TB), the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of TB was same as in absence of BCB. Explanation of this behavior is difficult, may be due to some electrostatic effect between the two.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the observed data, the following tentative mechanism may be proposed for photocatalytic bleaching of TB.

When the solution of the dye was exposed to light, in presence of zinc oxide, initially the ${}^1\text{TB}_0$ molecules are excited to first excited singlet state (${}^1\text{TB}_1$). Then there excited molecules are transferred to the triplet state through inter system crossing (ISC). The triplet dye (${}^3\text{TB}_1$) may donate its electron to the semiconductor and the dye becomes positively charged. The dissolved oxygen of the solution will pull an electron from

the conduction band of the semiconductor, thus, regenerating the semiconductor.

The OH^- will react with hole of the semiconductor to generate $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals will convert the triplet dye molecules into products, which are colorless. The participation of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals as an active oxidizing species was confirmed by carrying out same reaction in presence of some hydroxyl radical scavengers like 2-propanol, where the rate of bleaching was drastically reduced.

Conclusion :

The TB and its mixture with BCB in dye effluents can be efficiently photodegraded by ZnO photocatalyst, in short duration. The total (TB + BCB) rate of photocatalytic bleaching increases. The photodegradation efficiency depends upon the initial concentration of TB, pH, amount of semiconductor, light intensity, etc.

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Reference

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